

Privacy-Preserving Hyperparameter Tuning for Federated Learning

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ABSTRACT In this paper, we study the open problem of privacy-preserving hyperparameter (HP) tuning for cross-silo federated learning (FL). We first perform a comprehensive measurement study and benchmark various single-shot HP tuning strategies compatible with privacy-preserving FL pipelines. Our experimental results show that the optimal parameters of the FL server, e.g., the learning rate, can be accurately and efficiently tuned based on the HPs found by each client on its local data. We demonstrate that HP averaging is suitable for iid settings, while density-based clustering can uncover the optimal set of parameters in non-iid ones. Then, to prevent information leakage from the exchange of the clients' local HPs, we design and implement PRIVTUNA, a novel framework for privacy-preserving HP tuning using multiparty homomorphic encryption. We use PRIVTUNA to implement privacy-preserving federated averaging and density-based clustering, and we experimentally evaluate its performance demonstrating its computation/communication efficiency and its precision in tuning hyperparameters.

INDEX TERMS Federated learning, homomorphic encryption, hyperparameter optimization, privacy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Federated learning (FL) has become a promising approach for collaboratively training machine learning models on data originating from multiple clients (parties) without data outsourcing [1], [2]. During the FL process, each client trains a local model on its sensitive data and communicates a model update with a central server that computes the global machine learning model by averaging the received updates. While recent research has exhaustively studied the convergence of the global model for various distributed learning algorithms [1], [3], [4], [5], little effort has been devoted to tuning hyperparameters (HPs) which might affect the performance and accuracy of FL given its collaborative nature [6], [7]. Traditional HP tuning techniques, such as grid/random search or Bayesian optimization, due to their iterative operation, introduce significant computation and communication overhead making them impractical for FL settings. Moreover, their tuning performance on heterogeneous, non-iid data remains unclear.

Although the FL training process ensures that sensitive data does not leave the clients' local premises, recent research

has shown that it does not provide strong levels of privacy as model updates leak information about the training data [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16]. To mitigate the risk of privacy leakage, researchers have proposed privacy-preserving federated learning (PPFL) solutions employing privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) such as (i) differential privacy (DP) [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], (ii) secure multiparty computation (MPC) [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], or (iii) homomorphic encryption (HE) [34], [35], [36]. While all these solutions are crucial for preserving data privacy in FL, they assume that HPs, such as learning rate and momentum, are somehow predefined and configured. Performing HP tuning in the presence of PETs for FL becomes even more challenging given their *modus operandi*, e.g., DP solutions need to spend a significant portion of the privacy budget on the HP tuning itself, while MPC/HE approaches incur significant communication/computation overhead and thus cannot tolerate additional training iterations for HP tuning. As a result, there is a need for efficient HP tuning solutions for PPFL.

FIGURE 1. Our HP tuning method for cross-silo federated learning. hp_k and hp_g denote the local best HP configuration at client k and the global best configuration (denoted by g), respectively.

Existing *efficient* HP tuning methods for FL, such as FLoRa [37], rely on the *single-shot* HP tuning paradigm: Each client locally discovers its optimal set of hyperparameters and communicates it to the central server that decides the most suitable HPs for FL before the training process starts. However, sharing local HPs with the FL server might result in new forms of privacy leakage as prior work has shown that data samples with special attributes, e.g., outliers, can noticeably skew the optimal HP configuration and remain vulnerable to privacy attacks such as membership inference [38]. While employing noise-based techniques during HP tuning is a potential solution [38], [39], these might severely degrade the utility and the performance of the trained model, highlighting the need for efficient methods that ensure both privacy and accuracy in federated HP tuning.

In this work, we aim to address this research gap by proposing an efficient and accurate method for tuning HPs in cross-silo FL, compatible with PPFL pipelines. Following the single-shot HP tuning paradigm [37], we let each client discover their optimal HPs locally and we combine them in a privacy-preserving manner at the central server (Fig. 1). To understand how to combine client-found local HPs at the server side, we conduct a comprehensive measurement study across various datasets and model architectures, simulating both iid and non-iid FL settings, and benchmark diverse strategies. Inspired by aggregation methods commonly used in FL, we employ a variety of strategies such as computing the mean [2], the median [40], [41], the trimmed mean [40], trimmed mean/median with the highest validation accuracy, and density-based clustering [42], [43], and we compare their performance. Our study reveals that HP averaging is simple and effective for iid settings, while density-based clustering identifies optimal HPs in non-iid settings. Then, to protect the privacy of the clients' local HPs (hence, their sensitive data) we design a novel framework, PRIVTUNA, that facilitates their privacy-preserving combination at the server using multi-party homomorphic encryption (MHE) techniques. We use PRIVTUNA to implement two privacy-preserving

combination strategies for HP tuning, i.e., federated mean and density-based clustering, and we evaluate its performance in terms of computation/communication overhead and HP tuning precision.

The primary contributions of this paper are the following: (i) a comprehensive measurement study on various datasets, model architectures, and settings, that benchmarks various HP combination strategies on these settings and investigates the link between the HPs of the clients and the FL server, (ii) the identification of two efficient strategies for tuning the server hyperparameters based on the optimal HPs discovered by each client: (a) collective averaging for iid settings, and (b) density-based clustering for non-iid, which outperform prior work following a similar paradigm [37], (iii) the design of PRIVTUNA, the first framework for privacy-preserving hyperparameter tuning for FL based on multi-party homomorphic encryption (MHE) techniques, and (iv) the evaluation of PRIVTUNA on two privacy-preserving strategies, i.e., federated mean and density-based clustering, in terms of computation/communication overhead and hyperparameter tuning precision. Our implementation and supplementary results can be found at <https://github.com/sinemsav/hyperparams>.

Paper Organization: The rest of the paper is organized as follows: We describe the problem under investigation and the roadmap of our solution in Section II. We detail the methodology, experimental setup, and results of our measurement study in Section III. We introduce PRIVTUNA, a novel framework for privacy-preserving HP tuning in FL in Section IV. We review the related work on HP tuning for centralized and decentralized machine learning and discuss the privacy aspects of HPs in Section V. After we discuss various promising directions for future work in Section VI, we conclude in Section VII.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND ROADMAP

We discuss the problem statement (Section II-A) and the roadmap of our approach (Section II-B).

A. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We consider a cross-silo federated learning (FL) setting, where several (tens or hundreds of) entities (e.g., hospitals) aim at collaboratively training a machine learning model on their sensitive data. To this end, they need to employ a privacy-preserving federated learning (PPFL) solution where the aggregator receives model updates enhanced with a privacy-enhancing technology, e.g., differential privacy, secure multi-party computation or homomorphic encryption (see Supplemental Material A.1). To ensure the convergence and performance of the trained model, the entities need to tune hyperparameters (HPs) related to the learning process **before** the training starts. The HP tuning process should be efficient, accurate, and respect the privacy of each client's sensitive data (see Supplemental Material A.2).

Federated learning requires tuning both server- and client-side HPs: server-side HPs update the global model (Line 9, Algorithm 1, Supplemental Material A.1), while client-side HPs guide local training iterations. In this work, we focus

Algorithm 1: Single-Shot HP Tuning for Cross-Silo FL.

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1: for Each client  $S_i \in S$  do
2:   Perform LHO for all HPs in the set  $\{hp\}$   $\triangleright$  Client
   executes
3:   Send the best  $(\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i)$  pairs found by
   LHO to the server
4: end for
5:  $\{hp\}_g = \text{Combine}(\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i)$   $\triangleright$  Server
   executes

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on the problem of configuring **server-side hyperparameters**, e.g., server learning rate or momentum, since these play a significant role in the accuracy of the global model, especially when PPFL solutions are employed. For instance, differentially private solutions introduce noise in the learning process, thus these HPs need to be adapted accordingly [38], while secure multi-party computation and homomorphic encryption (HE) approaches require the approximation of non-polynomial functions (e.g., activations) whose performance is affected by these HPs [29], [34], [35], [36], [44], [45], [46]. As an example, POSEIDON [35] employs a least-squares approximation of non-polynomial activation functions within a specific interval to facilitate their execution under HE. Our observations indicate that appropriately adjusting the learning rate is crucial for selecting this interval, as a higher learning rate causes gradient values to exceed the interval boundaries quickly, leading to imprecise executions.

B. ROADMAP

To address the efficient, accurate, and privacy-preserving hyperparameter tuning problem for cross-silo FL, we follow a single-shot approach similar to [37] which is based on the hypothesis that an effective HP configuration for the global model can be derived from the client-specific local HPs. Thus, our idea is to infer optimal global HPs based solely on HPs discovered by the clients locally. Algorithm 1 presents the high-level overview of our approach for efficient HP tuning in cross-silo FL settings: (i) Each client performs local optimization (LHO) to tune the HPs in the set $\{hp\}$ on its dataset. Then, (ii) each client communicates the optimal sets of HPs along with an indicator of their performance (e.g., the accuracy achieved on a local validation set) to the server. Finally, (iii) the server combines (**Combine**(\cdot), Line 5) the HP sets received from all the clients to derive the optimal global hyperparameters $\{hp\}_g$.

Aiming to find effective strategies to combine (i.e., **Combine**(\cdot), Line 5, Algorithm 1) the client local hyperparameters and derive the optimal global hyperparameters at the server side, we perform a comprehensive measurement study to better understand the connection between local and global HPs in FL based on various factors such as the dataset, the model architecture, the client configuration, and the data distribution (Section III). Through our measurement study, we benchmark various strategies which infer server HPs from the

client HPs and which are compatible with privacy-preserving FL pipelines. Inspired by aggregation methods commonly used in FL, we experiment with combination strategies such as computing the mean [2], the median [40], [41], the trimmed mean [40], trimmed mean/median with the highest validation accuracy, and density-based clustering [42], [43]. Then, to address the privacy concerns raised by sharing local HPs with the FL server, we introduce PRIVTUNA, a novel framework that enables the HP combination at the server side in a privacy-preserving manner (Section IV). PRIVTUNA is based on multi-party homomorphic encryption (MHE) and can be used to develop various HP tuning techniques for FL with strong privacy guarantees. We use PRIVTUNA to develop two HP combination strategies that our measurements indicated as promising approaches, and we evaluate their performance in terms of computation/communication overhead, and HP tuning precision.

III. EVALUATING SINGLE-SHOT HP TUNING STRATEGIES FOR FEDERATED LEARNING

We begin with a measurement study to understand the relation between the client and server HPs in various FL settings by benchmarking various single-shot HP tuning strategies. Following our roadmap (Section II), the aim of the measurement study is to discover strategies for combining (i.e., **Combine**($\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i$), Line 5, Algorithm 1) the client optimal HPs and to derive the appropriate server HPs. We describe our methodology (Section III-A), then we discuss our experimental setup (Section III-B) and the corresponding results (Section III-C).

A. METHODOLOGY

To benchmark combination methods and find a suitable one for the global HP tuning based on the local HPs discovered by the clients, we conduct a measurement study on various datasets with different neural network architectures simulating both iid and non-iid FL settings. Our measurement study follows the subsequent footprint: (i) We first perform local HP optimization (**LHO**) per client to derive the optimal HPs on local datasets. We also perform global HP optimization (**GHO**) using federated grid search to construct a *ground truth* for the optimal server HPs. Then, (ii) following Algorithm 1, we employ various combination strategies to derive the server HPs based on the local HP optimization results of each client (i.e., their $\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i$ pairs). The tuning strategies that we benchmark for the **Combine**(\cdot) method of Algorithm 1 are the following:

Mean: Inspired from vanilla **FedAvg** [2], we compute the mean of the HPs obtained by LHO at each client.

Median: Based on the (coordinate-wise) median aggregation rule for robust FL [40], [41], we adopt a method that estimates the median of the HPs obtained by LHO at each client.

Trimmed-mean: We apply a similar strategy to the trimmed-mean aggregation rule for FL [40]. We discard the top and

bottom 10% of HPs (sorted by value) obtained through LHO at each client, then compute the mean of the remaining HPs.

Mean/Median of Best HPs: We rank each client’s HPs by validation accuracy, select the top 5%, and compute their mean or median on the server side.

DBSCAN: Following recent work on clustered FL [42], [43], we apply density-based clustering—suited to low-dimensional data and robust to outliers (see Supplemental Material A.3)—to group the top HPs from LHO at each client by validation accuracy. We use the cluster centroids as the final HP set.

Finally, (iii) we compare the results of each HP combination strategy with the ground truth baseline (i.e., the **GHO**), aiming to identify the most suitable methods for various settings.

B. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We describe the datasets that we use (Section III-B1), the model architectures (Section III-B2), the FL settings (Section III-B3), and the HPs and their configurations (Section III-B4) for our measurement study. All experiments are implemented in Python, using the FedJax library [47] for the FL operations.

1) DATASETS

We employ four datasets and we perform HP tuning based on validation accuracy which measures the model’s ability to predict labels for a validation set that constitutes a subset of the original training data. We list the datasets below:

MNIST: The MNIST [48] dataset is a popular collection of 28×28 pixel grayscale images of handwritten digits across 10 classes (0–9), with 60K training samples and 10K test samples.

Extended MNIST (EMNIST): EMNIST [49] is an extension of the MNIST dataset that contains a total of $\sim 814K$ 28×28 pixel grayscale images of handwritten characters including upper- and lower-case letters and digits. The number of classes is 62.

Street View House Numbers (SVHN): SVHN [50] is digit recognition dataset which contains 32×32 RGB images of house numbers collected by Google Street View. The training and test datasets comprise approximately 100K digits.

CIFAR-10: CIFAR-10 [51] contains 60 K 32×32 -pixel RGB images labeled across 10 categories (e.g., cat, ship, dog, etc.).

2) MODEL ARCHITECTURES

In our study, we rely on 3 neural network architectures:

Network A: This model consists of two sequential convolutional layers with a kernel size 5×5 , and 32 output channels followed by an average pooling (with window shape 2, stride of 1), and a dense layer with 64 neurons. The model has a total of 54,274 parameters. We use Network A in all experiments with MNIST.

Network B [52]: This model consists of two sequential convolutional layers with kernel size 5×5 , and 6 and 16 output channels, respectively. We use average pooling (with a window shape of 2 and stride of 1) and two dense layers of 120 and 84 neurons, respectively. We use Network B in all experiments with EMNIST and SVHN dataset. The EMNIST and SVHN models have 29,896 and 32,756 parameters, respectively.

Network C: The model consists of six sequential convolutional layers with kernel size 5×5 using average pooling (with window shape 2 and stride 1), and a dense layer with 128 neurons. The model has a total of 699,018 parameters. We use dropout, a regularization method that randomly omits units during the training. We use Network C in experiments with the CIFAR-10 dataset.

3) FEDERATED LEARNING SETTINGS

Our measurement study accounts for both iid and non-iid FL settings. To simulate the former we equally and randomly distribute the original dataset to N clients with $N = [10, 20, 50]$. To simulate a more realistic FL deployment, we consider a non-iid environment with $N = [10, 20]$ clients. Non-iid refers to data that is not independently and identically distributed across samples. In other words, the data is not drawn from the same distribution and the samples are not independent of each other. We generate various non-iid distributions following the methods described in [52] to account for label, feature, and quantity skews:

Label Skew: The label distributions vary across clients. Each client i is allocated a proportion p_i of the samples of each label according to a Dirichlet distribution (Dir_N), where $p_i \sim \text{Dir}_N(\beta_\ell)$. In our experiments, we use $\beta_\ell \in \{0.1, 1.0, 5.0\}$.

Feature Skew: The feature distributions vary across clients. First, we partition randomly and equally the dataset among each client i . Then, each client’s local dataset is subjected to varying degrees of Gaussian noise n_i to generate distinct feature distributions, where $n_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \frac{\beta_f * i}{N})$. In our experiments, we use $\beta_f \in \{0.02, 0.1\}$.

Quantity Skew: The size of the local dataset varies across clients. Each client i is allocated a proportion q_i of the total data samples according to a Dirichlet distribution, where $q_i \sim \text{Dir}_N(\beta_q)$. We use $\beta_q \in \{0.1, 0.4, 1.0, 2.0\}$ for our experiments.

In all of the above cases, the distribution parameter β used to generate diverse levels of data skew has the following property: a smaller β value results in greater heterogeneity among the clients.

4) HYPERPARAMETERS AND GRIDS

We focus on the server learning rate and momentum, conducting both LHO and GHO (ground truth) grid searches. Table 1 presents the grids used in our experiments. We fix one parameter and conduct a grid search on the other, given the time-intensive nature of these experiments. The remaining

FIGURE 2. Barplots of learning rate and momentum for the non-iid setting with $N = 20$ clients, variable datasets and **Combine(-)** strategies. The top-row results are for feature skew ($\beta_f = 0.02$), middle-row results for label skew ($\beta_l = 1.0$), and bottom-row results are for quantity skew ($\beta_q = 0.4$). Bar colors represent the HPs derived using various combination strategies. (a) Learning rate with feature skew ($\beta_f = 0.02$). (b) Momentum with feature skew ($\beta_f = 0.02$). (c) Learning rate with label skew ($\beta_l = 1.0$). (d) Momentum with label skew ($\beta_l = 1.0$). (e) Learning rate with quantity skew ($\beta_q = 0.4$). (f) Momentum with quantity skew ($\beta_q = 0.4$).

TABLE 1. Hyperparameter (HP) Grids for LHO and GHO

HP	Grid
learning rate	iid $\rightarrow [0.001, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5]$
	non-iid $\rightarrow [0.01, 0.03, 0.05, 0.1, 0.3, 0.5]$
momentum	iid $\rightarrow [0, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9, 0.92, 0.93, 0.95]$
	non-iid $\rightarrow [0, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9]$

HPs are kept constant: client learning rate at 0.01, client momentum at 0.01, number of epochs at $e = 30$ (for both LHO and GHO), and local iterations at $\ell = 2$ for GHO experiments. We keep 10% of the training data as a validation set. For the specified grid sizes, each experiment requires $7 \times 7 = 49$ training rounds for iid and $6 \times 4 = 24$ rounds for non-iid. Thus, the LHO experiments require $N \times 49$ and $N \times 24$ training rounds per client. In total, we conducted over 4,067 experiments for the iid and 6,912 for the non-iid settings.

C. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We showcase the results of our measurement study on both iid (Section III-C1) and non-iid (Section III-C2) cross-silo

FL settings. Then, we compare the tuning performance of the strategies identified by our measurement study with the state-of-the-art efficient HP tuning method for FL, FLoRA (Section III-C3). Finally, we discuss the main takeaways of our measurement study (Section III-C4).

1) IID SETTING RESULTS

We display our results on the iid setting for learning rate and momentum with $N = [10, 20, 50]$ clients using the **Mean** strategy as the **Combine(-)** method in Fig. 1, Supplemental Material B. We observe that the learning rate or momentum determined by applying the **Mean** strategy on the client HPs closely approximates the ground truth, and the resulting HPs do not hinder the achieved test accuracy (Fig. 1(c), Supplemental Material B). We note that obtaining the optimal learning rate and momentum on the CIFAR-10 dataset is more challenging than on other datasets; we speculate that this is due to the more complex classification task. Moreover, we observe that discovering the optimal server HPs from the client HPs is more difficult with an increasing number of clients; this is because the dataset size at each client decreases as the number of clients increases, i.e., the HPs that they locally discover are less *optimal*. This is also reflected on

FIGURE 3. Barplots of learning rate, momentum, and accuracy, for the non-iid setting with label skew ($\beta_\ell = 1.0$), using DBSCAN as the Combine(-) strategy on various datasets and experiments. The ground truth (GHO results) is indicated by black dots. Bar colors represent the results of combining the clients’ optimal HPs with the DBSCAN strategy, for a variable number of clients (N). (a) Learning rate. (b) Momentum. (c) Accuracy.

Fig. 1(c) in Supplemental Material B which shows that the test accuracy slightly decreases with an increasing number of clients, however, the HPs obtained by the **Mean** strategy yield similar accuracy to the (GHO) ground truth. Finally, we note that other combination strategies (e.g., median or DBSCAN) worked equally well for the iid setting indicating that in this case there is an inherent connection between the server HPs and the client ones. We omit the corresponding results due to space constraints.

2) NON-IID SETTING RESULTS

Fig. 2 showcases our measurement results for various **Combine(-)** strategies, datasets, and non-iid settings with $N = 20$ clients: (i) feature skew with $\beta_f = 0.02$ (top-row), (ii) label skew with $\beta_\ell = 1.0$ (middle-row), and (iii) quantity skew with $\beta_q = 0.4$ (bottom-row). We provide the same experiments with different skew parameters in Fig. 2, Supplemental Material B. Overall, we observe that straightforward combination strategies, such as computing the mean, its trimmed version, or the median, yield HPs that are not close to the ground truth; this demonstrates the challenge of performing HP tuning in non-iid settings. However, we observe that other combination strategies perform better: DBSCAN optimally derives the ground truth server learning rate across all skews and datasets, while the mean/median of the top 5% performs well for estimating the server momentum. For instance, the DBSCAN combination strategy perfectly matches the ground truth for learning rate (Fig. 2(a), (c), and (e)) as well as the momentum in experiments with the SVHN and EMNIST datasets (Fig. 2(b), (d), and (f)). Similarly, the mean/median of the top 5% HPs achieves the best results for estimating the momentum when there is feature or label skew on the MNIST and CIFAR10 datasets. When we consider the joint optimization of learning rate and momentum, across all our experimental settings with various skew types and parameters, datasets, and the number of clients, we find that, on average, DBSCAN outperforms the other combination strategies. Specifically, among 144 experiments, DBSCAN achieves the lowest absolute distance from the ground truth in 95 cases when evaluating the absolute distance of HP estimates from the ground truth for each combination function. The second best approach was the mean/median of the top 5% with 25 experiments achieving the lowest absolute distance.

Having identified DBSCAN as a promising combination strategy for non-iid settings, we perform further experiments to investigate how various factors affect its performance. Fig. 3 shows its results for a label skew setting with $\beta_\ell = 1.0$ while similar plots for feature and quantity skew can be found in Supplemental Material C (Figs. 3 and 4). We observe that the learning rate or momentum determined through DBSCAN closely approximates the ground truth optimal HP with a slightly higher deviation for momentum values. This deviation could be due to the utilization of a smaller grid for momentum experiments, which results in more pronounced shifts from one value to another. Nonetheless, the resulting HP adjustments do not have a substantial effect on the achieved test accuracy, as illustrated in Fig. 3(c) (and Figs. 3(c) and 4(c) in Supplemental Material C for feature and quantity skew, resp.). For example, in the quantity skew setting, the test accuracy achieved with the HPs determined by DBSCAN is exactly the same as that achieved with the ground truth HPs (GHO) in 7 out of 8 experiments (Fig. 4(c), Supplemental Material C).

3) COMPARISON WITH PRIOR WORK

We perform a comparison between the best-performing combination strategy, i.e., DBSCAN, and the closest related work, FLoRa [37]. FLoRa [37] is an HP tuning solution for FL that leverages local HP tuning to derive optimal global HPs (θ^*). Its one-shot approach and suitability for non-iid settings make it ideal for comparative analysis. In FLoRa, each client i performs local HP tuning and sends (HPs, validation loss) pairs E_i to the aggregator. Then, the aggregator constructs a unified loss surface $l : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ using the pairs E_i and finds the best HP configuration $\theta^* \leftarrow \operatorname{argmin}_{\theta \in \Theta} l(\theta)$. The authors propose four ways of constructing such loss surfaces, which we re-implement within our experiments for a fair comparison:

Single global model (SGM): All E_i sets are merged and used to train a global regressor $f : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. The loss surface is $l(\theta) = f(\theta)$.

Single global model with uncertainty (SGM+U): All E_i sets are merged and used to train a global regressor that provides uncertainty quantification around its predictions $f : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, u : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$, where $f(\theta)$ is the mean prediction of the model at θ and $u(\theta)$ quantifies the uncertainty around this

FIGURE 4. Comparison of the various combination strategies proposed in FLORA [37] vs. the density-based clustering (DBSCAN) strategy identified in our measurement study. The blue bar indicates the federated grid search results as ground truth. Each plot represents a different skew type (averaged across skew parameters with 10 and 20 clients). (a) Validation accuracies averaged across the quantity skew setting. (b) Validation accuracies averaged across the feature skew setting. (c) Validation accuracies averaged across the label skew setting. (d) Validation accuracies averaged across all skews.

prediction. The loss surface is defined as $l(\theta) = f(\theta) + \alpha * u(\theta)$ for some $\alpha > 0$.

Maximum of per-party local models (MPLM): This approach trains a regressor $f_i : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for each client set E_i . The loss surface is defined as $l(\theta) = \max f_i(\theta)$.

Average of per-party local models (APLM): This approach trains a regressor $f_i : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for each client set E_i . The loss surface is defined as $l(\theta) = \text{average} f_i(\theta)$.

All trained regressors are Random Forest ones, except for SGM+U, which trains a Gaussian Process regressor with a radial basis function kernel. We compare the validation accuracies of the models trained with (a) our derived global HPs, (b) FLORA-derived global HPs, and (c) the optimal, global HPs found by GHO. Fig. 4 shows the average validation accuracies achieved among various skew types (Fig. 4(a), (b), and (c)) and among all skew types (Fig. 4(d)). Comparing the validation accuracy achieved with the HPs estimated by the DBSCAN combination with various FLORA approaches, we find that, on average, and for each skew individually, our strategy outperforms FLORA across all datasets. The feature skew experiments for the SVHN dataset are deemed to be especially challenging for FLORA (note the high uncertainty indicated by the error bars). Compared to the optimal HPs found by GHO, our strategy achieves near-perfect results on all datasets except CIFAR-10, the most challenging dataset in our experiments. (see Section III-C1). Moreover, we observe that the label skew (Fig. 4(c)) is more challenging than other skews (Fig. 4(a) and (b)) which is compliant with the findings of Li et al. [52].

4) TAKEAWAYS

We conducted extensive experiments in both iid and non-iid cross-silo FL settings, aiming to identify a suitable

Combine(\cdot) strategy for deriving the server HPs from the client ones. We found that in iid settings, server HPs have a straightforward relationship with client HPs, and a simple averaging strategy achieves good performance. Averaging HPs is inspired by FedAvg [2], where combining local updates produces a global model that aligns with the shared data distribution in iid settings. Similarly, HPs affect optimization paths, and averaging them can yield a global HP that balances the effects of individual client and server settings. This approach ensures consistency and stability, leveraging the theoretical alignment of optimization under iid conditions.

In contrast, the non-iid setting poses a more challenging scenario, and simple combination strategies do not derive optimal sets of server HPs. Our experiments show that, on average, density-based clustering outperforms other combination strategies, while taking the mean or median of the top 5% of client HPs uncovers the optimal momentum values. In experiments with various non-iid settings, we found that HP tuning under label skew is the most challenging, as it leads to the largest decrease in model accuracy compared to other skews. On the other hand, model accuracy under quantity skew shows robustness to parameter variations, as data distribution remains consistent across clients, with only sample quantity varying between them. Regarding the datasets, we found that performing HP tuning on the EMNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets is more challenging than the rest. This is because the classification tasks are harder given the variety of samples and outputs. Finally, we compared our density-based clustering strategy, identified in our study, with the state-of-the-art FLORA [37] across various non-iid settings. On average, DBSCAN proved to be more effective, achieving validation accuracy close to that of the model trained with optimal HPs.

IV. PRIVACY-PRESERVING HYPERPARAMETER TUNING FOR FEDERATED LEARNING

Our measurement study (Section III) provided interesting insights into the connection between the client and server HPs in various FL settings. Moreover, it allowed us to establish simple and efficient techniques for tuning the server HPs by combining the optimal client HPs. However, revealing optimal client HPs to the FL server introduces a new privacy attack surface, as prior research indicates that specific data samples, such as outliers, can heavily influence HP optimization and become susceptible to inference attacks [38]. To address this, we introduce a novel framework, PRIVTUNA, which enables privacy-preserving HP tuning techniques using multiparty homomorphic encryption (MHE). We use our framework to implement and experimentally evaluate the two main strategies, i.e., averaging and density-based clustering. Our framework is flexible and easily extensible to other HP tuning techniques that might be discovered by researchers. We provide background information on MHE and its primary operations in Supplemental Material A.4. We describe PRIVTUNA and how it supports the execution of combination strategies for HP tuning among multiple clients (Section IV-A). Then, we experimentally evaluate PRIVTUNA in terms of runtime and communication overhead, as well as HP tuning precision (Section IV-B).

A. PRIVTUNA DESCRIPTION

We first provide a high-level overview of PRIVTUNA (Section IV-A1) and show how it enables the privacy-preserving execution of the two HP combination strategies, i.e., federated mean (Section IV-A2) and DBSCAN (Section IV-A3), that our measurement study identified as promising for iid and non-iid cross-silo FL settings, respectively. We also discuss how PRIVTUNA can be extended to other HP tuning strategies (Supplemental Material C).

1) PRIVTUNA OVERVIEW

Our approach for efficient HP tuning in cross-silo FL (Algorithm 1) relies on (i) the clients to perform local hyperparameter optimization (LHO) on their dataset, and to send the resulting HP sets to the server, and (ii) the server to combine (**Combine**(\cdot), Line 5, Algorithm 1) the received HP sets and derive the optimal global HPs for the FL process. To enable this workflow in a privacy-preserving manner, PRIVTUNA encrypts all LHO results and executes the combination strategy **under encryption** using MHE functionalities summarized in Supplemental Material A.4. As such, PRIVTUNA ensures that neither the server nor other clients can directly access the HP values discovered by LHO at each client.

PRIVTUNA operates as follows: (i) The clients generate their secret keys (**SeKeyGen**(1^λ)) and interact with each other to generate a collective public key (**DKeyGen**($\{sk_i\}$)) and possibly additional evaluation keys required to execute the combination function under encryption. (ii) Each client encrypts its LHO results (i.e., the (HP, accuracy) pairs) with the

Algorithm 2: Private Federated DBSCAN (PF-DBSCAN).

Grid Setup:

- 1: **for** Each client S_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ **do**
 - 2: Preprocessing: MinMax scaling of HPs
 - 3: $M_i \leftarrow \text{Discretize}(\{hp\}_i)$:
 - 4: Precompute *the closest cell map* $Cell_i$
 - 5: $M_i \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, M_i)$
 - 6: Send M_i to the server
 - 7: **end for**
 - Aggregation – Round 1:** ▷ Server executes
 - 8: $M \leftarrow \text{Add}(M, M_i), \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
 - 9: Create dense cell mask: $D \leftarrow \text{Compare}(M, \text{MinPts})$
 - 10: Send D to the clients
 - 11: $D \leftarrow \text{DDecrypt}(D, \{sk_i\})$
 - Local Clustering:**
 - 12: **for** Each client S_i with $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ **do**
 - 13: $LD_i \leftarrow D \odot M_i$
 - 14: Move non-dense *points* to the closest dense cell
 - 15: Merge adjacent cells to form final local clusters
 - 16: Create grid $HP_{ij}, \forall j \in \{hp\}_i$, and accuracies A_i
 - 17: Create matrix T_i with total number of points in each cluster
 - 18: $HP_{ij} \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, HP_{ij}), \forall j \in \{hp\}_i$
 - 19: $A_i \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, A_i), T_i \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(pk, T_i)$
 - 20: Send $HP_{ij}, \forall j \in \{hp\}_i, A_i, T_i$ to the server
 - 21: **end for**
 - Aggregation – Round 2:** ▷ Server executes
 - 22: $HP_j \leftarrow \text{Add}(HP_j, HP_{ij}), \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}, \forall j \in \{hp\}_i$
 - 23: $T \leftarrow \text{Add}(T, T_i), A \leftarrow \text{Add}(A, A_i), \forall i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$
 - 24: $HP_j \leftarrow \text{Divide}(HP_j, T), \forall j \in \{hp\}$
 - 25: $A \leftarrow \text{Divide}(A, T)$
 - 26: Send $HP_j, \forall j \in \{hp\}, A$ to the clients
 - 27: $HP_j \leftarrow \text{DDecrypt}(HP_j, \{sk_i\})$
 - 28: sort HP_j w.r.t. A
-

collective public key and communicates the resulting ciphertexts to the server. (iii) The server executes the **Combine**(\cdot) function on the received ciphertexts, taking advantage of the homomorphic properties of the underlying encryption scheme. (iv) The server interacts with the clients that collectively decrypt (**DDecrypt**($c, \{sk_i\}$)) the global HPs. We note that the evaluation of certain **Combine**(\cdot) strategies under encryption introduces challenges due to the limited arithmetic operations supported by the MHE scheme. In the following, we describe how to construct private versions of federated mean and density-based clustering combination strategies in PRIVTUNA.

2) PRIVATE FEDERATED MEAN (PF-MEAN)

Computing the mean of the HPs discovered by LHO at each client requires their summation and division by the number of HP values contributed. If the number of contributed HP values is known in advance (e.g., if each client only sends a

single best HP), then computing the mean under encryption is straightforward: It only requires homomorphic additions (i.e., $\text{Add}(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$) and a homomorphic multiplication by a constant, i.e., the (plaintext) inverse of the number of clients, using $\text{Mul}_{pt}(c_{pk}, p)$. However, in PRIVTUNA, we assume that each client can contribute multiple LHO results (e.g., their top $x\%$ HP sets based on validation accuracy). Thus, PRIVTUNA executes the PF-Mean computation by letting each client encrypt the sum of each HP in the slots of one ciphertext and an additional ciphertext indicating how many HP sets they are contributing. Then, the server computes the mean of each HP by performing additions that are inherently supported by the CKKS scheme and on the division operation ($\text{Divide}(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})$) that is possible with Goldschmidt's algorithm [53]. Note that excluding the key generation protocol ($\text{DKeyGen}(\{sk_i\})$), the PF-Mean computation in PRIVTUNA requires a single communication round: Each client sends its optimal HPs encrypted to the server, the server performs the summation and the division and returns the encrypted result to the clients for collective decryption.

3) PRIVATE FEDERATED DBSCAN (PF-DBSCAN)

Performing density-based clustering under encryption at the server side is challenging; DBSCAN requires the homomorphic evaluation of multiple non-linear operations, i.e., comparisons, which makes its privacy-preserving realization impractical. To avoid this issue, we leverage a federated density-based clustering [54] that enables collective clustering by all the clients. This algorithm operates as follows: It partitions the feature (i.e., HP) space into a grid with cells of a fixed granularity L , a parameter analogous to \mathcal{E} in traditional DBSCAN (see Supplemental Material A.3). Then, each client reports the number of points within the grid cells to the aggregation server. The server aggregates these by summing up the number of points in each cell, and creates/expands clusters across neighboring cells based on MinPts . Finally, each client receives the cluster label of each cell within the feature space. In the following, we enhance this algorithm with privacy protection using MHE and modify its workflow by offloading operations that are not supported by the CKKS scheme to the client side.

Algorithm 2 displays the privacy-enhanced version of the federated DBSCAN. The process starts after the clients perform LHO to obtain $(\{hp\}_i, \{accuracy\}_i)$ pairs and after they establish their cryptographic keys. The algorithm proceeds in four stages:

Grid Setup: Initially, each client preprocesses by retaining the HPs with the best validation accuracy and scaling them to $[0,1]$ using a MinMax scaler. This step is pivotal for a homomorphic comparison operation required later in the algorithm. Then, each client performs discretization (Line 3, Algorithm 2) and creates a grid of cells represented as a matrix M_i ; this matrix is populated by the total number of points inside each cell. A point is defined by HP values; for example, the learning rate and momentum form a two-dimensional point.

Each client then computes *the closest cell map* $Cell_i$ for each point, retaining a *point* \rightarrow *closest cell* mapping. The closest cell is determined by the shortest Euclidean distance between the point and its neighboring cells. To prevent the leakage of the HP grids, each client encrypts M_i and sends it to the server (Lines 5 and 6, Algorithm 2). By using the encoding (packing) capability of the MHE scheme, one matrix is encrypted into a single ciphertext, with each ciphertext slot representing a matrix entry.

Aggregation – Round 1: After the collection of the encrypted M_i matrices from the clients, the server aggregates (i.e., homomorphically sums) the grids and homomorphically compares each cell with the threshold MinPts to discover the *dense* cells (Line 9, Algorithm 2). To enable this under encryption, PRIVTUNA employs the approximate comparison scheme proposed by Cheon et al. [55]. The server then sends the encrypted dense mask (with 0s for sparse cells and 1s for dense cells) to the clients for collective decryption (Line 11, Algorithm 2).

Local Clustering: Upon receiving the dense cell mask D , each client identifies its local dense cells by multiplying it with M_i . If a dense cell has no data points, clients check $Cell_i$ to validate whether the mapped “closest cell” qualifies as dense. If the closest cell is dense, the client retains the data point, assigning its value to the nearest cell; otherwise, the point is excluded. This filters points eligible for clustering, i.e., those within or mapped to dense cells via the *closest cell map*. Non-dense points that are retained are assigned to the nearest adjacent dense cell to prevent two clusters from connecting through a point from a non-dense cell. Each client then merges adjacent cells by selecting a cell, adding all its neighbors to a queue, and checking if each queued cell is zero or non-zero. (Line 15, Algorithm 2). Subsequently, each client populates the dense cells with HPs and accuracy values of the retained data points, creating a matrix for each HP and an additional matrix for validation accuracies (Line 16, Algorithm 2). Finally, the clients record the total number of points in each cluster (required for averaging and deriving the final HP values). Each client encrypts their HPs and accuracies into a single ciphertext leveraging the packing capability of CKKS and encrypts the final count matrices. These two ciphertexts are sent to the server (Lines 18-20, Algorithm 2).

Aggregation – Round 2: The server aggregates the matrices, computing the average HPs and corresponding accuracy to determine the final global configuration on a single packed-ciphertext (Lines 22-25, Algorithm 2). For averaging, we use the Divide operation with Goldschmidt's iterative algorithm [53]. The averaged HP and accuracies are sent to clients, who collaboratively decrypt them. Finally, clients use the decrypted average accuracy matrix to rank and finalize the HP values (Line 28, Algorithm 2).

B. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

We experimentally evaluate PRIVTUNA with a focus on the runtime performance, communication overhead, and (HP tuning) precision, of the private federated mean (PF-Mean) and

TABLE 2. Microbenchmarks With $N=10$ Clients, $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$

Operation	Mean \pm Std Dev [ms]
SecKeyGen(1^λ) (per client)	14.42 \pm 1.12
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) (pk generation)	49.27 \pm 3.79
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) ($[ek]$ generation)	872.18 \pm 14.38
Encrypt(pk, p)	180.94 \pm 9.41
Add(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	4.92 \pm 1.57
Mul _{ct} (c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	3.73 \pm 1.33
Divide(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	135.69 \pm 6.54
DBootstrap (protocol initialization)	91.42 \pm 4.62
Compare(c_{pk}, t_{pk}) (with bootstrapping)	3474.72 \pm 371.59
DDecrypt($c, \{sk_i\}$)	0.31 \pm 0.06

TABLE 3. Microbenchmarks With $N=20$ Clients, $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$

Operation	Mean \pm Std Dev [ms]
SecKeyGen(1^λ) (per client)	51.24 \pm 2.41
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) (pk generation)	370.14 \pm 3.09
DKeyGen($\{sk_i\}$) ($[ek]$ generation)	842.7 \pm 5.06
Encrypt(pk, p)	189.637 \pm 0.64
Add(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	71.024 \pm 12.55
Mul _{ct} (c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	3.49 \pm 1.27
Divide(c_{pk}, c'_{pk})	154.810 \pm 4.22
DBootstrap (protocol initialization)	185.85 \pm 4.39
Compare(c_{pk}, t_{pk}) (with bootstrapping)	5021.61 \pm 138.93
DDecrypt($c, \{sk_i\}$)	0.29 \pm 0.06

DBSCAN (PF-DBSCAN). We implement PRIVTUNA on top of the Lattigo [56] lattice-based (M)HE library. All experiments are executed on an Apple M2 Pro processor running at 3.49 GHz with 16 GB of RAM. We run our experiments with two HPs, i.e., server learning rate and momentum, and we simulate cross-silo FL settings with $N = 10$ and $N = 20$ clients and all the skew settings and datasets of Section III. We report timings for ring dimensions of both $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$ and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$. The ciphertext moduli are $Q \sim 2^{438}$ and $Q \sim 2^{880}$. These parameters achieve 128-bit security according to the HE standard [57]. For the PF-DBSCAN experiments, we set the grid cell granularity to $L = 0.15$ and $\text{MinPts} = 4$, except for the quantity skew setting, where $\text{MinPts} = 2$.

1) RUNTIME PERFORMANCE

We report total runtime results for two scenarios: one with 10 clients and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$ (Table 2), and another with 20 clients and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$ (Table 3), without accounting for communication delays. The larger ring size is employed to address the cryptographic noise accumulation that occurs with more clients. Note that the runtime of PRIVTUNA is independent of the number of HPs as it packs them in the same ciphertext and leverages on SIMD operations. PRIVTUNA executes PF-Mean among 10 clients in 1.6s ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$) and among 20 clients in 1.8s ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$). The total runtime for PF-DBSCAN among 10 clients is ~ 5.8 s ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$). For $N = 20$ clients and larger cryptographic parameters ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$), PRIVTUNA

runs PF-DBSCAN in ~ 18.3 s. Note that the timings do not include LHO as this process is performed on cleartext data and optimizations on the local HP search are out of the scope of this work. Tables 2 and 3 provide a more detailed microbenchmark of the cryptographic operations. We observe that **DKeyGen**($\{sk_i\}$) and **Compare**(c_{pk}, t_{pk}) are the most time-consuming operations. However, note that **DKeyGen**($\{sk_i\}$) is executed only once and that **Compare**(c_{pk}, t_{pk}) relies on an approximation with a circuit of large depth, necessitating the use of the **DBootstrap** operation to refresh the ciphertexts.

Consequently, PRIVTUNA demonstrates substantial efficiency in global HP tuning, with a computational delay of just a few seconds. In contrast, performing the same HP optimization (HPO) task in PPFL frameworks can take days or even months. For example, in a setting similar to ours (see Section III-B1) with 10 parties and the MNIST dataset, the HE-based FL framework POSEIDON [35] requires approximately 3 hours for a single training round. Therefore, conducting a global HP search with a grid size comparable to our experimental setup in an iid setting (with learning rate and momentum grids of size 7) would necessitate 49 training rounds, resulting in 147 hours of computation to tune the HPs. In the same setting, PRIVTUNA performs PF-DBSCAN among 10 clients in ~ 5.8 seconds.

2) COMMUNICATION OVERHEAD

The communication overhead of PRIVTUNA depends on the **Combine**(\cdot) strategy, and the number of clients. A single ciphertext with $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$ ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$) has a size of 2.62 MB (9.43 MB). We observe that the communication scales linearly with the number of clients. In PF-Mean, each client sends one ciphertext of size 2.62 MB encrypting the sum of the learning rate and momentum discovered by LHO, and another one encrypting the number of HP sets contributed, yielding a total of 5.24 MB per client and 52.4 MB for 10 clients. In PF-DBSCAN, each client sends 3 ciphertexts (one for Aggregation-Round 1 and two for Aggregation-Round 2), yielding a total of 7.86 MB and 28.29 MB per client without bootstrapping, for ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}, N = 10$) and ($\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}, N = 20$), respectively. Finally, the **DBootstrap**() operation, required for the comparison operations, incurs a communication cost of ~ 13.1 MB with $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}, N = 10$ clients. While PF-Mean does not utilize bootstrapping, PF-DBSCAN uses it 6 times. Note that the number of bootstrapping operations depends on the circuit depth and the degree of the approximations; less/more precise implementations require less/more bootstrapping operations.

3) PRECISION

We evaluate the precision of PRIVTUNA for HP tuning in the context of both PF-Mean and PF-DBSCAN. We quantify the distortion between the HPs discovered by the plaintext and encrypted federated versions using the mean squared error (MSE). PF-Mean incurs an MSE of $\sim 2.4 \times 10^{-4}$ for $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}, N = 10$ and $\sim 1.8 \times 10^{-4}$ for $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}, N = 20$

which is mainly due to the division algorithm. PF-DBSCAN, which involves an approximation of both division and comparison operations, yields an MSE of $\sim 3.2 \times 10^{-4}$ and $\sim 1.02 \times 10^{-3}$, for $\mathcal{N} = 2^{14}$, $N = 10$ and $\mathcal{N} = 2^{15}$, $N = 20$, respectively, underscoring the minimal distortion in tuning performance incurred by our framework.

V. RELATED WORK

We review related work on HP tuning for centralized and decentralized machine learning and discuss the privacy aspects of HPs.

Centralized Hyperparameter Tuning: Several well-established HP tuning techniques, such as grid search, exist for centralized data contexts [58], [59], random search [60], Bayesian [61] or evolutionary optimization [62]. However, adapting these techniques to FL is challenging due to their iterative nature; they require multiple rounds of model training, resulting in significant communication overhead in FL's collaborative training process. This overhead is exacerbated when privacy-enhancing technologies (e.g., MPC or HE) are used to strengthen the privacy of FL.

Decentralized HP Tuning: Several works focus on neural architecture search (NAS) solutions tailored to federated learning (FL). Khodak et al. propose weight-sharing techniques for FL-HP tuning [63], [64]. However, prior work shows that weight sharing in FL raises significant privacy concerns [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. Other works propose performing NAS offline [65], [66], i.e., before the federated training starts, or online [67], [68], i.e., the HPO and the training are done simultaneously. However, offline NAS for FL requires a high number of communication rounds while online ones introduce significant computation overhead [69]. We note that our focus is on tuning the FL server HPs and not the model architecture.

Zhang et al. automate FL-HP tuning, adjusting parameters like training rounds and client numbers while respecting application-specific preferences [70]. Agrawal et al. cluster FL clients based on their HPs, updated through a genetic algorithm [42]. Chen et al. propose an online *tuning while training* method, and Dai et al. adapt Bayesian optimization to FL by employing Federated Thompson Sampling (FTS) [71]. Mostofa proposes a representation matching scheme to reduce local-global model divergence and introduces adaptive HP tuning [72]. Kuo et al. suggest performing HP tuning on public proxy data to address the challenges of data heterogeneity and privacy [7]. While these solutions advance HP tuning in FL, they are unsuitable for PPFL, as they require access to the federated model, which is protected by PETs like MPC or HE in high-privacy settings. Moreover, they introduce significant communication and computation overhead which is exacerbated in the presence of PETs.

To address the communication efficiency issue of prior FL HP tuning approaches, Zhou et al. propose FLoRA, a single-shot HP tuning approach [37]. FLoRA discovers the optimal

server HPs based on the local HPs of the clients by projecting them to a unified loss surface with various techniques (see Section III-C3). Our work differs in two ways: (i) we employ as ground truth a realistic baseline through federated grid search, while FLORA only considers the default HP set of scikit-learn algorithms, and (ii) we introduce a novel framework for privacy-preserving hyperparameter tuning using multi-party homomorphic encryption while FLoRA does not prevent information leakage from the shared HPs.

Hyperparameters and Privacy: Papernot and Steinke demonstrate that the optimal HPs discovered on a dataset can leak information about its samples via membership inference attacks [38]. While the authors propose the usage of Renyi Differential Privacy to eliminate such leakage, this technique can severely degrade utility during HP tuning and introduce further challenges, e.g., tuning the DP parameters themselves. Koskela and Kulkarni use a random subset of the confidential data for HP tuning to achieve lower DP bounds and yield better privacy-utility trade-offs [73]. However, a recent auditing study reveals that the privacy bounds of previous DP-based HP tuning are not tight [74]. Mohapatra et al. show how the HP tuning process in DP settings can be integrated within the broader privacy budget allocation through adaptive optimizations [75]. Ding et al. develop a DP-HP tuning framework with constant privacy overhead, allowing the expansion of the HP search space without affecting the privacy loss [76]. All these studies, however, do not take the FL setting into consideration.

Privacy-Preserving Hyperparameter Tuning for FL: Zawad et al. [77] propose a proxy-based HP scheme that allows the tuning tasks to be executed on the server side using synthetic data. Their method, however, is tailored to client-side parameters, and sharing synthetic data raises additional privacy concerns [78], [79]. Seng et al. perform NAS and HP tuning using DP [80]. However, their solution operates in an online manner introducing additional communication overhead compared to single-shot HP tuning approaches.

VI. DISCUSSION

To enable efficient hyperparameter (HP) tuning for cross-silo federated learning (FL), our work follows a single-shot approach similar to [37] that is based on the hypothesis that an effective HP configuration for the global model can be derived from the clients' local HPs. While our empirical measurements supported this hypothesis and identified suitable combination strategies for iid and non-iid FL settings, a complementary theoretical analysis of the validity of these strategies along with further experiments in other experimental setups (e.g., with more clients) would be an interesting direction for future work. Moreover, our work focused on optimizing two server-side HPs (learning rate and momentum), primarily due to the time-intensive nature of conducting such experiments. Despite this, we believe that the PRIVTUNA can be extended to multiple other HPs, such as regularization

coefficients and batch size, along with their joint optimization. Another intriguing direction for future work is to adapt PRIVTUNA for network architecture optimization. Such extensions would enhance PRIVTUNA's versatility across a wider range of optimization challenges. Finally, while this study evaluated PRIVTUNA on image datasets, we plan to evaluate our methods' performance in other domains, such as text and tabular datasets. These analyses would provide valuable insights into the framework's robustness in diverse FL applications.

VII. CONCLUSION

We investigated the problem of privacy-preserving hyperparameter (HP) tuning in the context of cross-silo federated learning (FL). We first benchmarked various combination strategies through a comprehensive measurement study, on various datasets, model architectures, and FL settings, aiming to understand the relationship between the clients and the server HPs, in both iid and non-iid data settings. Our results allowed us to devise efficient methods based on aggregation and density-based clustering, suitable for deriving the optimal server HPs from the locally computed HPs at individual clients. Aiming to reduce the privacy leakage from the HP tuning process, we introduced PRIVTUNA, a novel framework based on multi-party homomorphic encryption that enables the private tuning of HPs in cross-silo FL settings with strong confidentiality requirements. We implemented two strategies from our measurement study, PF-Mean, and PF-DBSCAN, within PRIVTUNA and we experimentally demonstrated their efficiency and accuracy for federated HP tuning.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Konečný, H. B. McMahan, D. Ramage, and P. Richtárik, "Federated optimization: Distributed machine learning for on-device intelligence," 2016, *arXiv:1610.02527*.
- [2] H. B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, and B. A. Y. Arcas, "Federated learning of deep networks using model averaging," 2016, *arXiv:1602.05629*.
- [3] H. Yu, R. Jin, and S. Yang, "On the linear speedup analysis of communication efficient momentum SGD for distributed non-convex optimization," 2019, *arXiv:1905.03817*.
- [4] P. Jiang and G. Agrawal, "A linear speedup analysis of distributed deep learning with sparse and quantized communication," in *Proc. 32nd Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, Red Hook, NY, USA, 2018, pp. 2530–2541.
- [5] S. Wang et al., "Adaptive federated learning in resource constrained edge computing systems," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 37,6, pp. 1205–1221, 2019.
- [6] P. Kairouz et al., "Advances and open problems in federated learning," *Found. Trends Mach. Learn.*, vol. 14.1-2, pp. 1–210, 2021.
- [7] K. Kuo et al., "On noisy evaluation in federated hyperparameter tuning," in *Proc. Mach. Learn. Syst.*, 2023, pp. 127–144.
- [8] B. Hitaj, G. Ateniese, and F. Perez-Cruz, "Deep models under the GAN: Information leakage from collaborative deep learning," in *Proc. ACM SIGSAC Conf. Comput. Commun. Secur.*, 2017, pp. 603–618.
- [9] Z. Wang, M. Song, Z. Zhang, Y. Song, Q. Wang, and H. Qi, "Beyond inferring class representatives: User-level privacy leakage from federated learning," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Commun.*, 2019, pp. 2512–2520.
- [10] L. Zhu, Z. Liu, and S. Han, "Deep leakage from gradients," in *Proc. 33rd Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2019, pp. 14774–14784.
- [11] L. Melis, C. Song, E. De Cristofaro, and V. Shmatikov, "Exploiting unintended feature leakage in collaborative learning," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. Secur. Privacy*, 2019, pp. 691–706.
- [12] M. Nasr, R. Shokri, and A. Houmansadr, "Comprehensive privacy analysis of deep learning: Passive and active white-box inference attacks against centralized and federated learning," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. Secur. Privacy*, 2019, pp. 739–753.
- [13] B. Zhao, K. R. Mopuri, and H. Bilen, "iDLG: Improved deep leakage from gradients," 2001, *arXiv:2001.02610*.
- [14] A. Wainakh et al., "User-level label leakage from gradients in federated learning," *PETS*, vol. 2022, pp. 227–244, 2022.
- [15] J. Deng et al., "TAG: Gradient attack on transformer-based language models," in *Proc. Conf. Empirical Methods in Natural Lang. Process.*, 2021, pp. 3600–3610.
- [16] M. Balunović et al., "Lamp: Extracting text from gradients with language model priors," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2022, vol. 35, pp. 7641–7654.
- [17] R. Shokri and V. Shmatikov, "Privacy-preserving deep learning," in *Proc. ACM Conf. Comput. Commun. Secur.*, 2015, pp. 909–910.
- [18] W. Li et al., "Privacy-preserving federated brain tumour segmentation," in *Proc. Mach. Learn. Med. Imag.*, 2019, pp. 133–141.
- [19] M. Abadi et al., "Deep learning with differential privacy," in *Proc. ACM SIGSAC Conf. Comput. Commun. Secur.*, 2016, pp. 308–318.
- [20] H. B. McMahan et al., "Learning differentially private recurrent language models," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learn. Representations*, 2017.
- [21] K. Wei et al., "Federated learning with differential privacy: Algorithms and performance analysis," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur.*, vol. 15, pp. 3454–3469, 2020.
- [22] N. Wu et al., "The value of collaboration in convex machine learning with differential privacy," in *Proc. 2020 IEEE Symp. Secur. Privacy*, 2020.
- [23] W. Zheng, R. A. Popa, J. E. Gonzalez, and I. Stoica, "Helen: Maliciously secure cooperative learning for linear models," in *Proc. IEEE Symp. Secur. Privacy*, 2019, pp. 724–738.
- [24] L. T. Phong, Y. Aono, T. Hayashi, L. Wang, and S. Moriai, "Privacy-preserving deep learning: Revisited and enhanced," in *Proc. Appl. Techn. Inf. Secur.*, 2017, pp. 100–110.
- [25] L. T. Phong, Y. Aono, T. Hayashi, L. Wang, and S. Moriai, "Privacy-preserving deep learning via additively homomorphic encryption," *IEEE Trans. Inf. Forensics Secur.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 1333–1345, May 2018.
- [26] C. Zhang, S. Li, J. Xia, W. Wang, F. Yan, and Y. Liu, "BatchCrypt: Efficient homomorphic encryption for cross-silo federated learning," in *Proc. 2020 USENIX Conf. Usenix Annu. Tech. Conf.*, 2020, pp. 493–506.
- [27] K. Bonawitz et al., "Practical secure aggregation for federated learning on user-held data," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst. PPML Workshop*, 2016.
- [28] D. Reich, "Privacy-preserving classification of personal text messages with secure multi-party computation: An application to hate-speech detection," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2019, vol. 32.
- [29] S. Wagh, D. Gupta, and N. Chandran, "SecureNN: 3-party secure computation for neural network training," in *Proc. Privacy Enhancing Technol.*, 2019, vol. 3, pp. 26–49.
- [30] S. Wagh, S. Tople, F. Benhamouda, E. Kushilevitz, P. Mittal, and T. Rabin, "FALCON: Honest-majority maliciously secure framework for private deep learning," *PETS*, pp. 188–208, 2020.
- [31] B. Hie, H. Cho, and B. Berger, "Realizing private and practical pharmacological collaboration," *Science*, vol. 362, no. 6412, pp. 347–350, 2018.
- [32] T. Chen and S. Zhong, "Privacy-preserving backpropagation neural network learning," *IEEE Trans. Neural Netw.*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 1554–1564, Oct. 2009.
- [33] H. Zhu, R. S. Mong Goh, and W.-K. Ng, "Privacy-preserving weighted federated learning within the secret sharing framework," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 198275–198284, 2020.
- [34] D. Froelicher et al., "Scalable privacy-preserving distributed learning," *Proc. Privacy Enhancing Technol.*, vol. 2, pp. 323–347, 2021.
- [35] S. Sav et al., "POSEIDON: Privacy-preserving federated neural network learning," in *Proc. Annu. Netw. Distrib. Syst. Secur. Symp.*, 2021.
- [36] S. Sav et al., "Privacy-preserving federated recurrent neural networks," *PETS*, vol. 4, pp. 500–521, 2023.
- [37] Y. Zhou, P. Ram, T. Salonidis, N. B. Angel, H. Samulowitz, and H. Ludwig, "Single-shot general hyper-parameter optimization

- for federated learning,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learn. Representations*, 2023.
- [38] N. Papernot and T. Steinke, “Hyperparameter tuning with renyi differential privacy,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learn. Representations*, 2022.
- [39] H. Wang, S. Gao, H. Zhang, W. J. Su, and M. Shen, “DP-HyPO: An adaptive private hyperparameter optimization framework,” in *Proc. 37th Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2024, pp. 41868–41891.
- [40] D. Yin, “Byzantine-robust distributed learning: Towards optimal statistical rates,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, 2018.
- [41] X. Chen, “Distributed training with heterogeneous data: Bridging median- and mean-based algorithms,” in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2020, vol. 33, pp. 21616–21626.
- [42] S. Agrawal, S. Sarkar, M. Alazab, P. K. R. Maddikunta, T. R. Gadekallu, and Q.-V. Pham, “Genetic CFL: Hyperparameter optimization in clustered federated learning,” *Comput. Intell. Neurosci.*, vol. 2021, Nov. 2021, Art. no. 7156420, doi: [10.1155/2021/7156420](https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/7156420).
- [43] C. Briggs, Z. Fan, and P. Andras, “Federated learning with hierarchical clustering of local updates to improve training on non-IID data,” in *Proc. 2020 Int. Joint Conf. Neural Netw.*, 2020, pp. 1–9.
- [44] B. Knott, S. Venkataraman, A. Hannun, S. Sengupta, M. Ibrahim, and L. van der Maaten, “Crypten: Secure multi-party computation meets machine learning,” in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2021, pp. 4961–4973.
- [45] M. Keller and K. Sun, “Secure quantized training for deep learning,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, 2022, pp. 10912–10938.
- [46] E. Hesamifard, H. Takabi, M. Ghasemi, and R. Wright, “Privacy-preserving machine learning as a service,” in *Proc. Privacy Enhancing Technol.*, 2018, vol. 3, pp. 123–142.
- [47] J. H. Ro, A. T. Suresh, and K. Wu, “FedJAX: Federated learning simulation with JAX,” 2021, *arXiv:2108.02117*.
- [48] Y. LeCun et al., “Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition,” *Proc. IEEE*, 1998, vol. 86, no. 11, pp. 2278–2324.
- [49] G. Cohen, S. Afshar, J. Tapson, and A. Van Schaik, “EMNIST: Extending MNIST to handwritten letters,” in *Proc. IEEE 2017 Int. Joint Conf. Neural Netw.*, 2017, pp. 2921–2926.
- [50] Y. Netzer, T. Wang, A. Coates, A. Bissacco, B. Wu, and A. Ng, “Reading digits in natural images with unsupervised feature learning,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2011.
- [51] A. Krizhevsky, *Learning Multiple Layers of Features from Tiny Images*, Toronto, Canada: University of Toronto, 2009.
- [52] Q. Li, Y. Diao, Q. Chen, and B. He, “Federated learning on non-IID data silos: An experimental study,” in *Proc. IEEE 38th Int. Conf. Data Eng.*, 2022, pp. 965–978.
- [53] R. Goldschmidt, “Applications of division by convergence,” M.Sc. thesis. *Massachusetts Inst. Technol.*, Cambridge, MA, USA, 1964.
- [54] G. Marino, “Federated dbscan,” Bachelor’s thesis, Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell’Informazione, Università di Pisa, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://github.com/GM862001/F_DBSCAN/tree/main
- [55] J. H. Cheon, D. Kim, and D. Kim, “Efficient homomorphic comparison methods with optimal complexity,” in *Proc. Adv. Cryptology*, 2020, pp. 221–256.
- [56] “Lattigo v5,” 2023 Accessed: Nov. 11, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/tuneinsight/lattigo>
- [57] M. Albrecht et al., “Homomorphic encryption security standard,” *Cryptology ePrint Arch.*, 2019, Paper 2019/939.
- [58] Y.A. Lecun, L. Bottou, G.B. Orr, and K.-R. Müller, “Efficient backprop,” in *Neural Networks: Tricks of the Trade. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 7700, G. Montavon, G.B. Orr, and K.-R. Müller, Eds., Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2012, doi: [10.1007/978-3-642-35289-8_3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-35289-8_3).
- [59] R. E. Bellman, *Adaptive Control Processes: A Guided Tour*. Princeton, NJ, USA: Princeton Univ. Press, 1961, doi: [10.1515/9781400874668](https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400874668).
- [60] J. Bergstra and Y. Bengio, “Random search for hyper-parameter optimization,” *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 13, no. 10, pp. 281–305, 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://jmlr.org/papers/v13/bergstra12a.html>
- [61] J. Mockus, V. Tiesis, and A. Zilinskas, “The application of Bayesian methods for seeking the extremum,” in *Proc. Optim. Techn. IFIP Techn. Conf. Novosibirsk*, 2014, pp. 117–129.
- [62] R. Bardenet and B. Kégl, “Surrogating the surrogate: Accelerating gaussian-process-based global optimization with a mixture cross-entropy algorithm,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, 2010, pp. 55–62. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:7130568>
- [63] M. Khodak et al., “Weight-sharing beyond neural architecture search: Efficient feature map selection and federated hyperparameter tuning,” in *Proc. 2nd SysML Conf.*, 2019.
- [64] M. Khodak et al., “Federated hyperparameter tuning: Challenges, baselines, and connections to weight-sharing,” in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2021, pp. 19184–19197. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=p99rWde9fVJ>
- [65] H. Zhu and Y. Jin, “Multi-time federated evolutionary federated learning,” in *Proc. IEEE Trans. Neural Netw. Learn. Syst.*, 2019, vol. 31.4, pp. 1310–1322.
- [66] M. Xu, Y. Zhao, K. Bian, G. Huang, Q. Mei, and X. Liu, “Federated neural architecture search,” 2020, *arXiv:2002.06352*.
- [67] C. He, M. Annaram, and S. Avestimehr, “Towards non-I.I.D. and invisible data with fednas: Federated deep learning via neural architecture search,” 2021, *arXiv:2004.08546*.
- [68] H. Zhu and Y. Jin, “Real-time federated evolutionary neural architecture search,” in *Proc. IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.*, 2021, vol. 26.2, pp. 364–378.
- [69] H. Zhu, H. Zhang, and Y. Jin, “From federated learning to federated neural architecture search: A survey,” *Complex Intell. Syst.*, vol. 7, pp. 639–657, 2021.
- [70] H. Zhang, M. Zhang, X. Liu, P. Mohapatra, and M. DeLucia, “Fedtune: Automatic tuning of federated learning hyper-parameters from system perspective,” 2022, *arXiv:2110.03061*.
- [71] Z. Dai, B. K. H. Low, and P. Jaillet, “Federated Bayesian optimization via thompson sampling,” in *Proc. 34th Int. Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2020, pp. 9687–9699.
- [72] H. Mostafa, “Robust federated learning through representation matching and adaptive hyper-parameters,” 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=SJeeL04KvH>
- [73] A. Koskela and T. Kulkarni, “Practical differentially private hyperparameter tuning with subsampling,” in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2024, vol. 36.
- [74] Z. Xiang, C. Wang, and D. Wang, “How does selection leak privacy: Revisiting private selection and improved results for hyper-parameter tuning,” 2024, *arXiv:2402.13087*.
- [75] S. Mohapatra, S. Sasy, X. He, G. Kamath, and O. Thakkar, “The role of adaptive optimizers for honest private hyperparameter selection,” in *Proc. AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell.*, 2022, pp. 7806–7813. [Online]. Available: <https://ojs.aaai.org/index.php/AAAI/article/view/20749>
- [76] Y. Ding and X. Wu, “Revisiting hyperparameter tuning with differential privacy,” 2022, *arXiv:2211.01852*.
- [77] S. Zawad, J. Yi, M. Zhang, C. Li, F. Yan, and Y. He, “Demystifying hyperparameter optimization in federated learning,” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=m7S4NvprHV1>
- [78] T. Stadler, B. Oprisanu, and C. Troncoso, “Synthetic data-anonymisation groundhog day,” in *Proc. 31st USENIX Secur. Symp.*, 2022, pp. 1451–1468.
- [79] M. Giomi, F. Boenisch, C. Wehmeyer, and B. Tasnádi, “A unified framework for quantifying privacy risk in synthetic data,” *Proc. Privacy Enhancing Technol.*, vol. 2, pp. 312–328, 2023.
- [80] J. Seng, P. Prasad, M. Mundi, D. S. Dhani, and K. Kersting, “Feathers: Federated architecture and hyperparameter search,” 2023, *arXiv:2206.12342*.

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